

Safety monitoring and adverse events form

Name of the school: _____

Name of teacher: _____ and contact:

- 1) Are there any positive behaviors or advantages you have noticed among students as a result of participating in the Informed Health Choices (Be Smart About Your Health) lessons?

- 2) Are there any negative behaviors or disadvantages that you have noticed among students as a result of participating in the Informed Health Choices (Be Smart About Your Health) lessons?

Thank you for completing this form